

EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

Two systems of extension coverage in southern Sri Lanka

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The Training and Visit (T&V) System for agricultural extension was introduced in Sri Lanka in 1979-80. Village extension workers (VEWs) of the Department of Agriculture had been carrying out village-level agricultural extension programs until 1990 when the VEWs were transferred to decentralized provincial councils. This study compares the extension coverage under the two systems in the southern rice-growing district of Matara.

We collected data for the main cropping seasons of 1986-87 and 1990-91 by interviewing 100 randomly selected rice farmers during each season.

Degree of interaction between VEWs and farmers was classified into no

Farmers (no.)

Extension coverage under different management systems, Matara, Sri Lanka.

interaction, one interaction in 3 mo, one in 2 mo, and one in 1 mo (see figure).

The number of farmers who did not interact with a VEW increased significantly under the new system. Farmers who had one interaction/month declined over the reference period. The χ^2 test

implies that a significant difference at 0.01 level exists between the two extension systems in terms of degree of interaction. The shift from T&V to the provincial council system resulted in declining extension contacts. ■

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Validation of BLASTSIM.2 model in IRRI blast (Bl) nursery and Cavinti, Laguna, Philippines

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We simulated leaf Bl epidemics under tropical conditions using BLASTSIM.2, a computer-based simulation model programed in FORTRAN. The model is potentially useful to understand development of Bl epidemics in different tropical rice management systems.

The model follows the typical leaf Bl monocycle consisting of stages (the state variables in the model) of spore production, spore release, spore deposition, latency, penetration and colonization, lesion production, and lesion development. Several interacting climatic,

Results of regression, correlation, and pooled-variance analyses of observed versus model-predicted lesion number/hill, lesion size/hill, and % disease severity/hill, 1989 WS and 1991 DS.^a

Treatment	State variable	R ²	r	F	Pooled variance
<i>Cavinti, 1989 WS</i>					
Low epidemic	Lesion no.	0.77	0.88**	255.08**	301.15 ns
	Lesion size	0.86	0.92**	460.96**	3.23 ns
	Severity	0.91	0.95**	797.37**	1.17 ns
Medium epidemic	Lesion no.	0.55	0.74**	95.92**	2673.87**
	Lesion size	0.61	0.78**	122.63**	20.44**
	Severity	0.73	0.86**	215.41**	8.91**
High epidemic	Lesion no.	0.76	0.87**	251.80**	2426.10*
	Lesion size	0.95	0.97**	1414.71**	15.21 ns
<i>IRRI, 1991 DS</i>					
10-cm spacing	Lesion no.	0.86	0.93**	516.31**	8669.35 ns
	Lesion size	0.94	0.97**	1409.70**	59.44 ns
	Severity	0.92	0.96**	990.07**	2.69 ns
20-cm spacing	Lesion no.	0.72	0.85**	215.23**	5.82 ns
	Lesion size	0.72	0.85**	217.34**	1254.83*
	Severity	0.77	0.88**	276.32**	0.07 ns

^ans = no significant difference, * = significant difference at 5%, ** = significant difference at 1%.

edaphic, and agronomic factors (the driving variables in the model) affect each stage and greatly influence the rate at which the monocycle moves.

BLASTSIM.2 has two main components: the BI simulation, where state variable values are computed, and the dew period estimation, which predicts the dew period and amount per day using DEWFOR, which was developed in the Netherlands. Simulation uses a daily time step process, invoking several driving functions at each time step to act on the state variables.

In BLASTSIM.2, crop variables such as plant height, leaf width, and leaf area are inputted as data sets to act as driving functions in B1 development. Simulation of epidemics was improved with the incorporation of genetics of host-pathogen relationship through the receptivity factor (RF), which is the ratio of the number of successful lesions/number of successful penetrations of germ tube.

BLASTSIM.2 has 12 modules and 1 graphics routine. The model requires two directory files (WTH.DIR for weather and BLEXP.DIR for treatment/experiment file), three input files (two files for weather variables and one file for crop

variables), three coefficient files for lesion expansion (LESLEN.BL), sporulation potential (SPORES.BL), and receptivity factor of specific host variety/pathogen isolate (H/P) combination (RECEPF.BL). The graphics interface files, FGRAPH.FI and FGRAPH.FD, and font file HELVB.FON, which come with the FORTRAN software, are also needed. BLASTSIM.2 runs in any microcomputer equipped with at least a 540K base memory, a math-coprocessor, a hard disk, and an EGA or VGA graphics adapter.

We validated the current version of BLASTSIM.2 using disease data from 1989 wet season (WS) at Cavinti for upland variety UPLRi-5 and from 1991 dry season (DS) IRRI B1 nursery experiments for BI-susceptible lowland cultivar IR72. Weather variables and crop data from each site were inputted along with RF values at different crop ages for these varieties interacting with *Pyricularia grisea* isolate PO6-6. Dew duration was estimated in model runs whenever leaf wetness data were not available.

Each simulation run was started with the observed number of lesions per leaf on a specific date. Differences between simulated and observed lesion number

and development and % disease severity expressed in per hill basis were analyzed using regression, correlation, and pooled variance tests.

The model accurately simulated leaf B1 progression in both Cavinti and IRRI B1 nursery trials (see table). Graphical displays showed close relationships between the field data and simulations in terms of curve shape and turning point. High values of R^2 and correlation coefficient (r) and highly significant F estimates suggest that simulated and observed disease variables for all treatments at either site did not differ. Although a pooled variance analysis gave highly significant variances in one treatment from Cavinti, the majority of treatments from the two experiments showed almost similar values and trends for model-predicted and field-measured variables.

It can be inferred that BLASTSIM.2 mimics the rice-leaf BI pathosystem, but further validation is needed to confirm this at other sites. Scientists interested in cooperating in this project are urged to write to the second author for a copy of the model and user document. Please specify microcomputer type and disk size. □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

IRRI announces group training courses for 1993

The IRRI Training Center will be offering a variety of courses on rice-related subjects in 1993. Courses are held at IRRI headquarters unless

otherwise noted. For information about a course, contact the Head, Training Center, International Rice Research Institute, P.O. Box 933, Manila 1099, Philippines. Fax: 63-2-818-2087. Space is available for trainees in the following courses:

Date	Course	Trainees (no.)
11-22 Jan	Rice Production for IRRI Staff	30
1 Feb-21 May	Hybrid Rice Breeding	28
1 Feb-26 Mar	International Network on Sustainable Rice Farming	20
26 Apr- 4 Jun	Engineering for Rice Agriculture	39
7 Jun-30 Jul	Weed Control (Direct-Seeded Rice)	9
19 Jul-10 Sep	Integrated Pest Management	25
23 Aug- 1 Oct	Irrigation and Water Management	25
4 Oct-26 Nov	Rice Production Research <i>Thailand</i> ^a	25
4 Oct-26 Nov	Rice Biotechnology ^a	15
4 Oct- 5 Nov	Rice Seed Health	8
15-26 Nov	Gender Analysis ^a	25
15-26 Nov	Research Management ^a	15

^aSpecial project-funded course.

Postdoctoral research fellow positions at IRRI

The International Rice Research Institute invites Ph D applicants for research fellow positions in the following fields:

Molecular biology. To improve soil N use efficiency through rice genotype selection, breeding, and soil management practices in the irrigated environment. The work involves tagging genes with molecular markers for higher biological N fixation, N uptake, and N use efficiency, and studying the mechanisms associated with those traits.

Candidates should have a Ph D degree in soil science, agronomy, plant genetics, or breeding with research experience in molecular biology. Place of work: IRRI headquarters in Los Baños. UNDP/World Bank-funded